

TRANSFORMORLARDA QUVVAT VA ENERGIYA YO‘QOTILISHLARI KASHAYTIRISH MAQSADIDA ELEKTR TARMOQLARDA KUCHLANISH DARAJALARINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH

Ataullayev Nodir Odilovich.

Navoiy Davlat Konchilik va Texnologiyalar Universiteti.

Elektr energetikasi kafedrası mudiri

Tog‘ayev Islom Bekpo‘lat o‘g‘li.

Navoiy Davlat Konchilik va Texnologiyalar Universiteti

Abdullayev Ulug‘bek Yoqubjon o‘g‘li.

Navoiy Davlat Konchilik va Texnologiyalar

Universiteti 5a-20 EE guruhi talabasi

***Annotatsiya.** Elektr tarmog‘ining quvvat transformatorlarida faol va reaktiv quvvat va energiya yo‘qotishlarining transformatorlarning turli yuklamalari ostida ularning kirishidagi kuchlanishga bog‘liqligi o‘rganildi. Transformatorlarning kirishlarida optimal kuchlanish ularning yuk koeffitsientiga va maksimal foydalanish vaqtiga qarab ulardagi quvvat va energiya yo‘qotishlarini minimallashtirish sharti bilan aniqlanadi.*

***Kalit so‘zlari:** Simsiz quvvat uzatish, induktiv ulanish, Qi standarti, A4WP, mikroto‘lqinli elektr uzatish..*

Kirish. Transformatorlardagi quvvat yo‘qotishlari bo‘sh ishlamay yo‘qotishlar va yuk yo‘qotishlaridan iborat. Bo‘sh yo‘qotishlar girdob oqimlari va histerezis yo‘qotishlaridan po‘latdagi yo‘qotishlar bilan bog‘liq. Po‘latdagi yo‘qotishlar induksiyalangan emf kvadratiga mutanosibdir, bu transformatorning birlamchi o‘rashining terminallaridagi kuchlanishga taxminan tengdir, chunki transformatorning birlamchi pallasida kuchlanishning yo‘qolishini e‘tiborsiz qoldirish mumkin. Transformatoridagi yuk yo‘qotishlari yuk oqimining kvadratiga proporsionaldir. Ushbu yo‘qotishlarni besleme kuchlanishini oshirish yoki transformatorning yuk kuchini kamaytirish, masalan, reaktiv quvvat komponentini qoplash orqali kamaytirish mumkin. Ammo shu bilan birga, po‘latdagi yo‘qotishlar va transformatorning magnitlanishining reaktiv kuchi ortadi.

Asosiy qism. Transformatorning kirishida optimal kuchlanishni aniqlaymiz, bunda transformatoridagi aktiv quvvatning umumiy yo‘qolishi minimal bo‘ladi. Nisbiy kuchlanish darajasiga qarab quvvat yo‘qotilishini ifodalash U^* va kuchlanish yo‘qolishining hosilasini nolga tenglashtirib, optimal kuchlanishni aniqlash uchun oddiy analitik ifodani olishimiz mumkin:

$$\Delta P_T = \Delta P_X U_*^2 + \frac{1}{U_*^2} \Delta P_K K_3^2 ; \quad \frac{d\Delta P_T}{dU_*} = 2\Delta P_X U_* - \frac{2}{U_*^3} \Delta P_K K_3^2 = 0 ;$$

$$U_{*opt}(3) = \sqrt{\frac{\Delta P_K K_3^2}{\Delta P_X}} ,$$

Bu yerda ΔP_X , ΔP_K - salt ish paytida va transformatorning qisqa tutashuvi paytida quvvat yo‘qotilishining pasport qiymatlari;

Formuladan (3) kelib chiqadigan bo‘lsak, transformatorning kirishidagi optimal kuchlanish uning yuklanish koeffitsienti K_z va bo‘sh turish va qisqa tutashuv yo‘qotishlar nisbati, ya’ni texnik xususiyatlari va yuklanishiga bog‘liq.

Transformator yuklamasining turli omillarini hisobga olgan holda, texnik ma'lumotlarga ega TDN 10000/35 tipidagi transformator uchun formula (3) bo'yicha optimal kuchlanishni hisoblaymiz: $S_{nom}=10000$ kVA; $U_{vn}=35$ kV; $U_{nn}=10,5$ kV; $\Delta P_X=14,6$ kVt; $\Delta P_K=65$ kVt. Optimal kuchlanishni hisoblash natijalari 1-jadvalda jamlangan.

Jadval 1. TDN-10000/35 transformatorining kirishidagi optimal kuchlanishning S yukiga bog'liqligi

$S, \text{ kVA}$	1000	3000	5000	7000	9000	11000	13000	14000
K_3	0,1	0,3	0,5	0,7	0,9	1,1	1,3	1,4
$U_{opt, \text{ kV}}$	0,460	0,797	1,029	1,217	1,380	1,526	1,659	1,722
$U_{opt, \text{ kV}}$	16,1	27,9	36	42,6	48,3	53,4	58,1	60,2

Transformatorning kirishidagi optimal kuchlanishning yuklanish omiliga bog'liqligi grafigi 1-rasmda ko'rsatilgan. Unda elektr tarmog'idan foydalanishning texnik shartlariga muvofiq kuchlanishni tartibga solishning ruxsat etilgan chegaralarini belgilab, biz transformatorning kirishida mumkin bo'lgan optimal kuchlanishni tartibga solish zonasini olamiz.

1-Rasm. Transformatorning kirishidagi optimal kuchlanishning $DRT = \min$ shartdagi yuklanish koeffitsientiga bog'liqligi.

1-rasmdan ko'rinib turibdiki, transformatorning kirishidagi optimal kuchlanish undagi yuklama ortib ketganda oshirilishi kerak. Ruxsat etilgan kuchlanish og'ishlari miqdori bo'yicha texnik cheklovlarni hisobga olgan holda, ma'lum turdagi transformator uchun optimal kuchlanish U_{opt} transformatorning nominal quvvatining (40 - 55)% oralig'idagi yuklamasiga mos keladi. Kattaroq yuklamalar bilan transformatorning kirishida izolyatsiyalash sharoitida maksimal ruxsat etilgan kuchlanish darajasini va kichikroq yuklama bilan - iste'molchilar uchun elektr energiyasining zarur sifatini ta'minlash sharti bilan minimal ruxsat etilgan darajani saqlash kerak.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

1. Тогаев И., Рахимова Ш., Розиков Ж. статистический анализ потерь электроэнергии на воздушных линиях электропередачи 6-10 кВ //international conference of education, research and innovation. – 2023. – т. 1. – №. 3. – с. 62-65.
2. Togayev I., Tursunova A., Eshmirzayev M. Monitoring of overhead power lines //international conference: problems and scientific solutions. 2022. -Т. 1. – №. 2. – с. 267-271.
3. Akram T., Islomjon T., Shahrizoda R. Energy Problems in uzbekistan. Their solutions and remedial measures //Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 273-277.
4. Ibodulaev, M., Tovboyev, A.N. Research of Ferro-Resonance Oscillations at the Frequency of Subharmonics in Three-Phase Non-Linear Electric Circuits and Systems//E3S Web of Conferences, 2020, 216, 01113 https://www.e3sconferences.org/articles/e3sconf/pdf/2020/76/e3sconf_rses2020_01113.pdf
5. Tog'ayev I.B., Isoqulov D.SH., Turniyozov Z.A. Monitoring of air power lines with an assessment of their condition // Central Asian Research Journal For Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS) ISSN (online): 2181-2454 Volume 2 | Issue 5 | May, 2022

6. Islomjon Bekpo‘lat o‘gli Togayev, and Tovbaev Akram Nurmonovich. "statistical analysis of power waste on 6-10 kv air power transmission lines." international journal on orange technologies 2.10: 92-94.

7. I Togayev, A Norqulov, S Shirinov. modern technologies for improving the quality of electricity. Results of national scientific research international journal 2 (2), 177-181

8. T Akram, T Islom, U Islombek. analysis of the impact of the installation of reactive power sources on the quality of electricity. Web of semantic: universal journal on innovative education 2 (2), 198-201